

Exoforge: Interdisciplinary teaching laboratory for the development of assistive technology projects

Lluís Bernat, Carlos A. Jara, Jose L. Ramon, Jorge Pomares, Gabriel J. Garcia, Andres Ubeda

Human Robotics Group, Department of Physics, Systems Engineering and Signal Theory, University of Alicante, Alicante, Spain

Email: lbi5@alu.ua.es, carlos.jara@ua.es, jl.ramon@ua.es, jpomares@ua.es, gjgg@ua.es, andres.ubeda@ua.es

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6924401>

Abstract

Today, the aging of the population and the prevalence of neuromuscular diseases make it increasingly necessary to develop technologies that improve the quality of life of these users and optimize the physical rehabilitation process. The initiative "Exoforge: Interdisciplinary teaching laboratory for the development of assistive technology projects" is proposed as a complementary training tool for engineers in the field of health technologies to cover these needs from a multidisciplinary orientation. From the teaching point of view, this initiative tries to address two essential aspects in the training of future engineers who work in the field of assistive technologies: multidisciplinary, through the incorporation of students from different degrees such as robotics engineering, biomedical engineering, or multimedia engineering; and job orientation and entrepreneurship, through the development of projects with the possibility of future transfer to a company and useful from a social point of view. This paper also describes the evaluation of the Exoforge initiative. From its creation, Exoforge has launched two different projects: ARMIA, a sensorized sleeve for upper limb rehabilitation; and ARES, a lower limb robotic exoskeleton. The main objective is to establish whether the initiative provides useful skills and tools to students within a complementary educational framework such as internships in laboratories at the University of Alicante or, where appropriate, the development of Undergraduate Thesis and Master's Dissertations related to the proposed projects.

Keywords: Active Learning; Engineering Education; Project Approaches.

1 Introduction

The number of people with congenital and/or acquired disabilities in today's Spanish society represents a large number of dependent people who lack the necessary autonomy for a fully independent life. The health technology sector is allocating a large part of its funding to provide the highest possible quality of life for these disabled people and the elderly. One of the most funded topics is the rehabilitation of the affected patient. However, according to the WHO (World Health Organisation), existing rehabilitation services have been disrupted in 60-70% of countries due to the Covid-19 pandemic. This disruption, and the need to avoid visits and attendance of patients in hospital or rehabilitation centres, reflects the importance of having competitive, reliable and accessible rehabilitation, tele-rehabilitation and home-based rehabilitation systems.

Exoforge is an interdisciplinary teaching laboratory for the development of projects in assistive technologies. It is a multidisciplinary laboratory in which students from different degrees develop projects in assistive technologies. Exoforge is a proposal that emerged within the Human Robotics research group at the University of Alicante during the 2020-21 academic year. Students participate in Exoforge through their internships as part of the curriculum of their own university degree. The participating students can come from the Degrees in Biomedical Engineering, Robotics Engineering and Multimedia Engineering, as well as from the Master's Degree in Automatics and Robotics. The main objectives of the Exoforge initiative are:

1. To develop a multidisciplinary complementary training experience for students in their final years of undergraduate and master's degrees.
2. To propose bridging experiences between educational sphere, and business and research spheres.
3. To promote innovation and entrepreneurship among students of the University of Alicante Degrees.
4. To enhance general skills such as teamwork, decision-making, personal initiative and social values and specific skills in different branches of knowledge.

Students at the Polytechnic School of the University of Alicante always have the possibility to do an internship in a company in the syllabus of their degree courses. Within the research groups of the University of Alicante,

students are offered the possibility to carry out these internships within the framework of current research projects. From the Human Robotics research group, we think that the best way to carry out these internships is through real projects that could be proposed by any company in the sector. In order to complete these projects, it is necessary to form a group of students, with great potential and who come from different degrees, that can collaborate to complement each other. The result of this proposal is Exoforge, which is similar to a company that "hires" the students. Within Exoforge, new projects are proposed every year. In the first year, Exoforge launched the ARMIA project. ARMIA is a project that develops a new wearable and wireless rehabilitation device based on an upper limb sleeve with inertial and electromyographic sensors. This device allows recording the patient's kinematic and muscular information during rehabilitation tasks and introduces telerehabilitation, a new paradigm in the process of recovering upper limb motor function. This device has significant advantages compared to other devices for motor rehabilitation. It includes low cost, small size, light weight, and wireless portability components. In the current academic year (2021-22), the development of ARMIA has continued, while a new project has been launched: ARES, a robotic exoskeleton for the lower limb.

These projects are related to the research lines of the Human Robotics research group. They are projects in which the professors of the research group can act as leaders and advisors at the same time. The idea is to take advantage of the Project Based Learning (PBL) methodology to enhance students' learning in a real project that they will be able to find in any company after graduation.

PBL is not a new teaching methodology. In (Postman, 1969) a teaching model was proposed in which lectures were abandoned and students developed their creative abilities through open questions and problems. These ideas were applied for the first time at the Mc Master University (Canada) and at the Case Western Reserve University School of Medicine (USA), where the name of problem-based learning methodology appeared for the first time. This method quickly spread through European Universities in the 1970s. It is in this decade when the Danish University of Aalborg developed a new method derived from problem-based learning: project-based learning (PBL). Currently, the PBL is considered one of the most suitable methods for the new higher education models based on active learning (Guo, 2020; Bittencourt, 2018; Guerra, 2017). With this methodology, students must assume greater responsibility, and obtain freedom of action. They will go through an active learning process that is necessary to solve the projects proposed by the teacher. PBL-based teaching is based on the development of a project that sets goals, such as the development of the final product, which achievement will require the learning of technical concepts and attitudes. The PBL methodology will only be in tune with the objectives of the European Higher Education Area (EHEA) if the student takes an active role in their learning process.

One of the main advantages of the PBL methodology is that it is developed in a real and experimental environment. This characteristic helps students to relate the theoretical contents with the real world, thus improving the acquisition of theoretical concepts. At the same time, the student takes an active role in the project and sets the pace and depth of their own learning, which makes this methodology perfectly applicable to groups with disparate base knowledge. The PBL motivates students, therefore, it can be considered as an instrument to improve academic performance and persistence in studies. Furthermore, the PBL creates an ideal framework to develop various transversal competences such as teamwork, planning, communication, and creativity (Lima, Dinis-Carvalho, Flores, & Hattum-Janssen, 2007; Powell & Weenk, 2003).

Only few works about PBL methodology in internship works are found in the literature. In (Johari, A., & Bradshaw, A. C., 2008) authors considered the roles of task, learner, and mentors as they are needed to make the most of project-based internship programs. Implications for the design and development of internship programs, and specifically successful student performance in internship programs, were also considered. Another paper describes G-DORM (Ueda, Y., et al., 2018). G-DORM is a student exchange project that has global PBL in an internship by Niigata University with four universities in Mekong countries. The paper describes the achievements of G-DORM carried out in 2017, in terms of coordination with companies for program designing, recruiting and selection of students, and implementation of internship in the student exchange program and evaluation.

2 Methodology

This section describes the methodology used in Exoforge during the last two years. Firstly, the students participating in each of the courses are described, detailing the grade they are studying. Next, the two projects launched during each course are described in more detail: ARMIA and ARES.

2.1 Participants

The students who have participated in the two courses in which Exoforge has offered internships come from the degrees taught at the Polytechnic School of the University of Alicante. The professors of the research group promoting Exoforge, Human Robotics, mainly teach on the Robotics Engineering Degree. That is why most of the students interested in participating in Exoforge come from this degree. They also teach on the Biomedical Engineering Degree, the Multimedia Engineering Degree and the Master's Degree in Automation and Robotics. In the 2020-21 academic year, Exoforge launched the ARMIA project. The aim of this project is to develop a sensorised sleeve that allows rehabilitation exercises to be carried out at a low cost and autonomously. The project mainly attracted the attention of robotic and biomedical engineers. The selection was made mainly based on the dossier provided by the candidates. Table 1 shows the number of students interested in participating, and the final number of students, from each grade who ended up participating in Exoforge during the 2020-21 academic year.

Table 4. Entry profile of students enrolled in the 2020-21 academic year in Exoforge.

Degree	Number of candidate students	Number of selected students
Robotic Engineering Degree	15	5
Biomedical Engineering Degree	8	2
Computer Science Engineering Degree	1	0
Master's Degree in Automation and Robotics	1	1

In the academic year 2021-22, Exoforge started by offering the extension of the ARMIA project. We already had a valid prototype, but we wanted to make progress in obtaining a textile sleeve that the user who was going to carry out the therapy could wear on his or her arm. In addition, the aim was to develop a serious game that, using the signals measured in the sensorised sleeve as input, would allow the exercises to be adjusted to the physical and mental fatigue of the user in the rehabilitation activities. This attracted students from the Multimedia Engineering Degree who had not shown interest in the first-year call. In addition, Exoforge has launched the ARES project for this academic year 2021-22, which consists of the design, simulation, and implementation of a knee exoskeleton. This other project is more robotic and attracted many students from the Robotics Engineering Degree. It also requires knowledge of biomechanics, which can be provided by Biomedical Engineering students. Table 2 shows the students interested by degree in participating in Exoforge during this academic year 2021-22, as well as the students who have finally participated in the two projects.

Table 2. Entry profile of students enrolled in the 2021-22 academic year in Exoforge.

Degree	Number of candidate students	Number of selected students
Robotic Engineering Degree	12	8
Biomedical Engineering Degree	6	4
Multimedia Engineering Degree	3	2

2.2 ARMIA project

ARMIA is a sensorised sleeve that allows measuring kinematics and muscular activity during upper limb movements. To determine arm kinematics three inertial sensors are placed on the kinematic chain: one on the

thorax (reference), one on the arm and one on the forearm. These last two sensors provide arm links orientation and elbow and shoulder joint angles. ARMIA does not provide wrist orientation, but it is possible to obtain Cartesian coordinates of the arm end effector (hand).

Muscular activity is measured from three of the main muscles in charge of upper limb movements: biceps, triceps and pronator teres. These sEMG sensors are used to determine the signal amplitude (contraction force) and other factors such as muscular fatigue. The instrumentation of these sensors is critical, as the bipolar electrodes must be placed parallel to the muscle fibers and close to the middle of the muscle belly, and the reference electrode must be firmly in contact with the skin.

ARMIA software is structured into three different levels. The low-level layer establishes the physical communication protocols between the different sensors and the microcontroller, and the wireless communication between the microcontroller and the computer. The medium-level layer manages the data acquisition and storage from the sensors. Finally, the high-level layer develops processing and visualization modules.

During the 2020-21 academic year, a first ARMIA prototype was developed (see Figure 1). During the academic year 2021-22, work is being carried out on a textile design for the wearable, as well as on a virtual reality application that will allow the user to carry out rehabilitation exercises.

Figure 1. ARMIA prototype.

During the first course (2020-21), the students assigned to the ARMIA project were separated into three different working teams:

- Design Team (2 robotics engineering and 1 Master's Degree in Automation and Robotics students):
 - Design and implementation of the initial prototype.
- Software Team (3 robotics engineering students):
 - Acquisition and communication.
- Neuromechanics Team (2 biomedical engineering students):
 - Biomechanical study from inertial and sEMG sensors.

During this course (2021-22), the students assigned to the ARMIA project have been separated into two different working teams:

- Design Team (3 robotics and 2 biomedical engineering students):
 - Adaptation of the first prototype to a textile wearable sleeve.
- Software Team (2 multimedia engineering students):
 - Design and development of a VR serious game.

2.3 ARES project

ARES is a project that proposes the design and development of a lower limb exoskeleton. The ARES exoskeleton was created with the aim of giving users with various disabilities the opportunity to regain their mobility,

improve their quality of life and increase their autonomy. Specifically, the exoskeleton has been designed to fit a patient's leg to allow and facilitate their movement. The exoskeleton integrates inertial and electromyographic sensors to detect the signals that the brain sends to the leg. The exoskeleton processes these signals to be able to move along with the limb and, in this way, to assist the patient during walking.

The main features of the ARES device are defined below:

- Robotic exoskeleton adaptable to different leg morphologies.
- Full integration of low-cost inertial and electromyographic sensors in the device.
- Control of the exoskeleton based on ROS (Robot Operating System).
- Acquisition and calibration software for intuitive configuration and use.
- Biomechanical study of human gait for planning valid trajectories for the exoskeleton.
- Design of gait patterns to assist the patient in the development of different types of movements.

The ARES device is designed to be used both by private users to recover their mobility and autonomy, and by hospitals, clinics, therapy centers and nursing homes. ARES is a lower limb exoskeleton designed for the rehabilitation of patients with different types of disability such as spinal cord injuries, neurodegenerative diseases or those who have suffered cerebrovascular accidents. In this first phase of development, the exoskeleton has a motorized kneecap with the aim of enabling functional recovery of the knee and thus improving their autonomy.

The ARES exoskeleton adjusts to different anthropometric measurements thanks to its adaptable design. It features an adjustable knee joint extension angle, allowing the full range of knee joint movements to be limited depending on the patient's characteristics. In addition, the adjustment is simple, and the fitting, adjustment and set-up can be done in a few minutes.

In addition, the ARES exoskeleton can be used as a rehabilitation therapy to complement traditional rehabilitation by generating constant gait patterns. Its use can contribute recovering the mobility of the knee or to maintain its functional capabilities as long as possible.

A first working prototype of the exoskeleton is now available (see Figure 2). All the software development of the project is being carried out in ROS. The use of ROS, and open-source software, allows the integration of previously existing developments in perception, planning and artificial intelligence.

Figure 2. ARES prototype.

The students assigned to the ARES project have been separated into three different working teams:

- Neuromechanics Team (2 biomedical engineering students):
 - Study of lower limb neuromechanics and design of motor movement patterns.
- Design Team (2 robotics engineering students):
 - Adaptation of the orthosis for the motor, design and 3D printing of the robot-orthosis motion transmission.

- Control and actuation Team (3 robotic engineering students):
 - ROS control and actuation of the Maxon motor via Ethercat, and motion pattern tracking.

3 Exoforge evaluation

For the drafting of the survey to evaluate different aspects of the methodology, we first thought of the items that were most interesting to know. A very important aspect to know was the group cohesion achieved, since all the work for the development of the project is divided into different work teams. Students were also asked for their opinion on whether they found the Exoforge experience useful, or whether it allowed them to apply the knowledge acquired in their degree, if the motivation has been increased or not, etc. Another important question to be evaluated is whether their time at Exoforge has given them any ideas for the development of their final degree project. The questions asked can be seen in Table 3. The survey was conducted through a questionnaire using Google Forms. This survey was anonymous, although as described in Section 2.1, the total sample is known, given that they are the students who have participated in the Exoforge experience. Although 18 students participated in the experience, only 11 answered the survey.

Table 3. Survey for the Exoforge initiative student opinion.

Q1	Do you feel you have learnt anything from working at Exoforge?	Yes	No
Q2	Have you been able to apply concepts seen in any of the subjects of the Degree in Exoforge?	Yes	No
Q3	Do you consider that the time spent on external internships is sufficient to carry out your tasks within Exoforge?	Yes	No
Q4	Do you consider that the guidance provided by the teachers for the resolution of the project has been adequate?	Yes	No
Q5	Doing my external internship at Exoforge has allowed me to define an idea for my Final Degree Thesis dissertation	Yes	No
Rate from 1 (a little) to 9 (a lot):			
Q6	The work methodology proposed in Exoforge has made me feel motivated.	1	2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9
Q7	The work methodology proposed at Exoforge promoted teamwork.	1	2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9
Q8	I have learned how to make a detailed planning of the time to be spent on each of the tasks required to complete the project	1	2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9
Q9	I have learnt how to carry out an analysis and design prior to project implementation	1	2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9
Q10	I have learnt to search for information on my own for the implementation of the project	1	2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9
Q11	I have learnt to work in a group and actively participate in the project	1	2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9
Q12	I am satisfied with the work we can do in the group formed in Exoforge	1	2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9
Q13	I like the working atmosphere of the group formed in Exoforge	1	2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9
Q14	I am satisfied with the amount of work being done at Exoforge	1	2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9
Q15	I am satisfied with the ideas that the members of the Exoforge group bring to the table when we work together	1	2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9
Q16	When one member of Exoforge's group doesn't understand something, the others try to explain it to him or her ---	1	2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9
Q17	The members of my group prefer to work together rather than working individually	1	2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9
Q18	Doing my internship at Exoforge gives me a work experience close to reality	1	2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9

The results of the survey are very encouraging. We will now review the results for each question. In the first question, the students unanimously indicate that they have learned something during their time at Exoforge (100%). Also, all students (100%) say that they have been able to apply the concepts seen in their degree courses during the 150 hours they have spent on the external internships carried out at Exoforge. Once again, all the students (100%) who answered the survey indicated that the 150 hours were sufficient to carry out the tasks that were planned at the beginning of the internship at Exoforge. With regard to question 4, the students also unanimously indicated that the lecturers have given them adequate guidance in the development of the proposed project (100%). Question 5 is the last Yes/No question. The idea behind this question was to obtain information on whether the students have seen or detected any ideas for a final degree project to be carried out based on the developments made in Exoforge. More than half (54.5%) answered in the affirmative, which seems to us a very interesting aspect, as Exoforge can become a seed for the development of small individual projects that enhance the experience started in the internships.

The first block of questions (Q6, Q8, Q9, Q10, Q14, Q18) with 11 possible Likert-type answers deals with the opinion of each student's individual work in Exoforge. For each question, students answer a value from 0 to 10 indicating a little (0) to a lot (10). Figure 3 shows the answers obtained for this first block of Likert-type questions. The answers are positive for all the questions in this block. Specifically, when asked whether the Exoforge methodology has motivated them, the majority indicate values between 8 and 10 (90.09%), with one isolated case indicating 5. All students indicate that the methodology used has helped them to some degree to learn to plan the time used for each task (with 100% indicating values between 7 and 10). The same happens when questioned about whether the methodology has helped them learn about the importance of prior design and analysis before starting to programme or develop tasks (also with 100% in values between 7 and 10, although in this case more than half 6/11 voted values of 9 and 10). Encouraging responses were also seen in question 10. The students claim to have learned to search for information on their own to solve the various tasks assigned in the project (7/11 voted values of 9 and 10). In question 14, the majority of students say that they are satisfied with the work carried out in Exoforge (9/11 voted 10, the other 2 voted 8). Finally, they were asked whether they think that the work done at Exoforge gave them an experience as close as possible to what they might find in the world of work. This is where we found the greatest disparity in the responses, although always with positive values (between 5 and 10).

Figure 3. Answers for Questions 6, 8, 9, 10, 14 and 18 of the survey.

The second block of questions (Q7, Q11, Q12, Q13, Q15, Q16 and Q17) with 11 possible Likert-type answers deals with group cohesion and group functioning. Figure 4 shows the answers obtained for this second block of Likert-type questions. Again, the answers are positive for all the questions in this block. To begin with, in question 7, 9 of the 11 students who filled in the survey say that working at Exoforge encouraged teamwork (they voted values of 9 and 10). Of particular interest is question 11, where all students indicate that they have learned to work in a team because of their experience at Exoforge (all voted 8-10). The same is true for question 12, with all 11 students voting between 8 and 10, with 7 of the 11 voting 10 on the question of whether they

are satisfied with the work that can be done by the group formed in Exoforge. The working atmosphere is undoubtedly the most highly valued aspect of the survey, with 9 of the 11 students voting 10, and the other two, 8 and 9. The ideas contributed by the other members of the group to solve the problems encountered throughout the project are also highly valued (9/11 voted 9-10). Question 16 asks about companionship, asking whether the members of the group help someone who has not understood concepts to understand them (all students voted 8-10). Virtually all students indicate that others prefer to work in groups rather than individually (only one student voted 4, the rest 8-10).

4 Conclusion

The Exoforge initiative has allowed students from the Polytechnic School of the University of Alicante to carry out their internships for two academic years in technological projects for the rehabilitation of upper and lower

Figure 4. Answers for Questions 7, 11, 12, 13, 15, 16, and 17 of the survey.

limbs. The result of the first course (2020-21) was a success, obtaining a valid prototype of a sensorised sleeve that allows obtaining kinematic and electromyographic information during the rehabilitation task. In addition, this project, the ARMIA project, won the Impulso 2021 Prize for Accessibility, awarded by the University of Alicante. In this second course of the Exoforge initiative, ARMIA continues to develop the initial prototype to make it more "wearable", while a serious game for virtual reality is being developed to gamify the rehabilitation therapy exercises. In addition, during this academic year, the ARES project has been launched, in which a first functional prototype of a low-cost knee exoskeleton has already been obtained. This exoskeleton is controlled by free software and has a series of sensors that allow estimating the user's movement intention to improve the quality of rehabilitation and/or walking assistance. The survey carried out among the participating students shows excellent results. A great group cohesion in teamwork is observed, as well as great satisfaction in participating in the projects offered by Exoforge. More than half of the students are even considering continuing to develop tasks for Exoforge as part of their own final degree projects.

5 References

- Bittencourt, A. C., Diniz, A. C., & Macedo S.C. (2018). A review of Problem/Project-based learning approach in engineering education: motivations, results and gaps to overcome. In: PAEE/ALE, 2018, Brasília. International Symposium on Project Approaches in Engineering Education, 8, 302-308.
- Guerra, A., Ulseth, R., & Kolmos, A. eds. (2017). PBL in Engineering Education. Sense Publishers, Rotterdam.
- Guo, P., Saab, N., Post, L. S., & Admiraal, W. I. (2020). A review of project-based learning in higher education: Student outcomes and measures. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 102, art. no. 101586.
- Johari, A., & Bradshaw, A. C. (2008). Project-based learning in an internship program: A qualitative study of related roles and their motivational attributes. *Education Tech Research Dev*, 56, 329-359.
- Lima, R. M., Dinis-Carvalho, J., Flores, M. A., & Hattum-Janssen, N. v. (2007). A case study on project led education in engineering: students' and teachers' perceptions. *European Journal of Engineering Education*, 32(3), 337-347.
- Postman, N., & Weingartner, C. (1969). *Teaching as a subversive activity*. New York: Dell Publishing Co.
- Powell, P. C., & Weenk, W. (2003). *Project-Led Engineering Education*. Utrecht: Lemma.
- Ueda, Y., Tsuboi, N., Suzuki, T., Abe, K., Suzuki, T., Kourakata, I., & Nakano, S. (2018). W-06 Value Creation by Global Project-based Learning in Internship: Practices in G-DORM 2017, JSEE Annual Conference, Session ID W-06, 34-39.